

Electrochemical and biological behaviour of synthesized bioactive (2E)-3-(2-hydroxyphenyl)-N-(4-phenyl substituted)triaz-2-ene-1-carbothioamide

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Abstract : The electrochemical behaviour of substituted thiosemicarbazones has been investigated. A series of thiosemicarbazones (2E)-3-(2-hydroxyphenyl)-N-(4-substituted phenyl)triaz-2-ene-1-carbothioamide have been prepared. The structure elucidation was done by elemental and spectral analysis. The electro reductions of synthesized compounds have been also studied by cyclic voltammetry at glassy carbon electrode, which indicate the reducible behaviour from its cyclic voltammogram. The nature of electrochemical process of all the synthesized compounds were studied on DME and HMDE using polarography, cyclic voltammetry, and constant-potential coulometry techniques. The data revealed that the electrode process is irreversible and diffusion controlled. The kinetic parameters, i.e. charge transfer coefficient (α_{na}), formation constant ($k_{f,h}^0$) and diffusion coefficient were calculated. The synthesized compounds were also screened for antimicrobial activities.

Keywords : Thiosemicarbazones, differential pulse polarography, cyclic voltammetry, antimicrobial activity.

Introduction

Thiosemicarbazones have been reported to exhibit antitubercular activity^{1,2}. 1,3,4-Thiadiazoles and 1,3-thiazoles and their derivatives exhibit various biological activities such as antimicrobial³⁻⁵, anti-inflammatory⁶⁻⁸, anti-convulsant^{9,10}, antihypertensive^{11,12}, local anesthetic¹³, anticancer^{14,15}, hypoglycemic¹⁶, and cytotoxic activities¹⁷⁻²³. A phenyl thiosemicarbazide bearing methoxy and chloro moieties show good antimicrobial activity^{24,25}.

From last so many decades electroanalytical techniques have been applied for the study of redox mechanisms and in identification of biologically important compounds²⁶. It has been observed that biologically important compounds are usually electroactive or they can be easily transformed into electroactive substances.

In the present work, a series of (2E)-3-(2-hydroxyphenyl)-N-(4-phenyl substituted)triaz-2-ene-1-carbothioamide have been synthesized and the nature of electrochemical process of all the synthesized thiosemicarbazones were studied on DME and HMDE using po-

larography, cyclic voltammetry, and constant-potential coulometry techniques. The kinetic parameters, i.e. charge transfer coefficient (α_{na}), formation constant ($k_{f,h}^0$) and diffusion coefficient were also calculated. The present study comprised the *in vitro* antimicrobial screening of newly synthesized thiosemicarbazone compounds.

Results and discussion

The route followed for the synthesis of (2E)-3-(2-hydroxyphenyl)-N-(4-substituted phenyl)triaz-2-ene-1-carbothioamide in the laboratory was based on the condensation of aldehyde and primary aromatic amines (Scheme 1). The products were obtained in 80–85% yields and their characteristics physical properties have been presented in Table 1.

Differential pulse polarography :

A single reduction wave has been observed for all the synthesized compounds (1 to 3) at dropping mercury electrode in the pH range 2.5 to 10.0 assigning to the reduc-

Scheme 1

Table 1. Physical data of (2*E*)-3-(2-hydroxyphenyl)-*N*-(4-substituted phenyl)triaz-2-ene-1-carbothioamide

Compd.	R ¹	R	M.p. (°C)	Yield (%)	Mol. formula
1	-CH ₃		164	73	C ₁₅ H ₁₅ N ₃ OS
2	-OCH ₃		168	62	C ₁₅ H ₁₅ N ₃ O ₂ S
3	-Cl		155	75	C ₁₄ H ₁₂ N ₃ OSCl

tion of -CH=N group (Fig. 1). The peak potential shifted towards more negative potential with the rise in pH for all the compounds indicating the participation of protons in electrode process (Fig. 2). Plots of i_d vs pulse amplitude were linear passing through the origin confirming the diffusion controlled nature of the electrode process. On increasing the concentration of (2*E*)-3-(2-hydroxy-phenyl)-*N*-(4-substituted phenyl)triaz-2-ene-1-carbothio-amide $-E_{1/2}$ shifted towards more negative potential. This behavior clearly indicated towards irreversible nature of the electrode process, which is further confirmed by logarithmic analysis i.e. the slope of the plot of $[-E_{d.e.} \text{ vs } \log(i/i_d - i) - 0.546 \log t]$ is greater than $59.2/n$ mV. Differential pulse polarographic characteristics have been given in Table 2.

Cyclic voltammetry :

Cyclic voltammograms of 2-methoxy-4-[(*Z*)-{2-[(4-substituted phenyl)carbomthioyl]hydrazinylidene}methyl]

Mechanism of thiosemicarbazones formation

phenyl acetates (10^{-3} M) in BR buffer exhibit a single cathodic peak in the potential range -0.20 to -1.50 V, assignable to the reduction of -CH=N- group in the pH range 2.5 to 11.5 (Fig. 3). A small shoulder before the peak was due to the adsorption phenomenon. In this pH range no anodic peak could be observed indicating the irreversible nature of the electrode process.

Effect of scan rate :

The plot of i_d (μA) vs $v^{1/2}$ (v = scan rate) was found to be straight line passing through the origin, indicating the diffusion-controlled nature of the electrode process. The current function ($i_{pc}/v^{1/2}$) for -CH=N- group depends on the scan rates. The cathodic peak potentials were found to shift towards more negative potential with increasing scan rate, as expected for irreversible electron transfer.

Fig. 1. A typical differential pulse polarogram of 2-{2-hydroxybenzylidene}-*N*-(3-methoxyphenyl)hydrazinecarbothioamide at pulse amplitude 100 mV s⁻¹, conc. 2.0 × 10⁻³ M and pH 2.5.

Fig. 2. Plots of peak potential vs pH for 2-methoxy-4-[(Z)-{2-[(4-methylphenyl)carbamothioyl]hydrazinylidene}methyl]phenyl acetate at different pH, conc. 0.5 × 10⁻³ M and pulse amplitude 100 mV s⁻¹.

Effect of concentration :

For all the synthesized (2*E*)-3-(2-hydroxyphenyl)-*N*-(4-substituted phenyl)triaz-2-ene-1-carbothioamide the cathodic peak current increases linearly with concentration. The plot of i_{pc} vs concentration (Fig. 4) is a straight line which also supports the diffusion controlled nature of the electrode process.

Coulometry :

Controlled potential coulometry was employed for determining the number of electrons (n) transferred in the electrode process. Number of electrons n , were calculated from the charge consumed by the desired concentration of (2*E*)-3-(2-hydroxyphenyl)-*N*-(4-substituted phenyl)triaz-2-ene-1-carbothioamide. The charge consumed was determined in acidic medium. For this purpose 2 mL of 1 mM solution of the electroactive species was placed in the cell and electrolysis was carried out. During electrolysis, the solution was continuously stirred and purged with nitrogen. Number of electrons n was calculated using the equation $Q = nFN$, where Q is the charge in coulombs, F is the Faraday constant, and N is the number of moles of substrate.

Reaction mechanism :

On the basis of differential pulse polarography, CV and coulometry a mechanism has been postulated for the reduction of (2*Z*)-2-(4-hydroxy-3-methoxybenzylidene)-*N*-(4-substituted phenyl)hydrazinecarbothioamides. General sequences for addition of proton and electron viz. H⁺, e⁻, H⁺, e⁻ and H⁺, e⁻, e⁻, H⁺, the later is found to be more probable for these compounds (Scheme 2).

Antimicrobial study of thiosemicarbazones :

It was clearly evident from Table 3, in the thiosemicarbazone analogs, the most potent activity has been shown by compound, bearing two methoxy groups against the tested pathogens in the order of *A. niger*, *C. albicans*, *S. aureus*, *B. antracis*. Simultaneously, com-

Table 2. Differential pulse polarographic characteristics for 2-methoxy-4-[(Z)-{2-[(4-substituted phenyl)carbamothioyl]hydrazinylidene}methyl]phenyl acetate at pulse amplitude 100 mV s⁻¹, pH 2.5

Conc. × 10 ⁻³	Peak	-R	-E _p (V)	i _d (µA)	α _{na}	I	∂E _{1/2} /∂pH (V/pH)	D ₀ ^{1/2} × 10 ⁻⁴ (cm ² s ⁻¹)	k _{f,h} ⁰ (cm s ⁻¹)
0.5	-CH=N	-CH ₃	0.97	11.6	5.91	1.878	0.038	1.5 × 10 ⁻⁶	6.39 × 10 ⁻⁴
1	-CH=N	-OCH ₃	0.81	13.02	20.59	7.89	0.058	6.4 × 10 ⁻⁶	8.87 × 10 ⁻⁴
0.5	-CH=N	-Cl	0.89	8.89	1.59	5.387	0.053	4.4 × 10 ⁻⁶	1.05 × 10 ⁻³

Fig. 3. Cyclic voltammetry of 2-methoxy-4-[(Z)-{2-[(4-substituted phenyl)carbamothioyl]hydrazinylidene}methyl]phenyl acetate.

Fig. 4. Plot of i_d vs concentration of (2E)-N-(4-chlorophenyl)-3-(2-hydroxyphenyl)triaz-2-ene-1-carbothioamide at pH 6.5, ν 100 mV s^{-1} .

pound with chloro, methoxy and methyl groups present in aldehydic portion with chloro substitution in thiosemicarbazide also showed appreciable zone of inhibition against the tested pathogens. It has further been found that withdrawal of the above bio labile groups from the parent compound reduce the activity against the tested pathogens. Antitubercular efficacy of synthesis compound was also found comparable to the standard drugs for *S. aureus*. Among the tested compounds, methoxy and chloro group in the thiosemicarbazone series showed highest activity in the order *C. albicans* > *S. aureus* > *B. antracis* > *A. niger* at 800 $\mu\text{g}/\text{disc}$ concentration. The compound shows assuring antifungal activity in *C. albicans* and *S. aureus* than the standard drug fluconazole.

The MIC value determination was also carried out for

the target compounds, and results are presented in the Table 3. It was observed that the thiosemicarbazone series was more active and showed better activity in comparison to the reference drug.

Experimental

All the chemicals were obtained from Aldrich Chemical Co., Germany. KCl (1.0 mol L^{-1}) solution was prepared in distilled water and used as supporting electrolyte. Stock solutions of synthesized (2E)-3-(2-hydroxyphenyl)-N-(4-substituted phenyl)triaz-2-ene-1-carbothioamide were prepared in ethanol and DMF. A series of Britton-Robinson buffers in the pH range 2.5 to 11.0 were prepared. The readymade pre-coated TLC silica gel plates from E. Merck, Germany were used for TLC separation. The differential pulse polarographic studies were carried out using 2.0 mL stock solution of depolarizer, 1.0 mL of 1 M KCl, and 7.0 mL of appropriate buffer. The influence of several buffers (phosphate, Britton-Robinson and acetate buffer) on the analytical signals was also studied and it was found that the reduction peaks were well defined in BR buffer. The microbial sensitivity has been assessed by using disc diffusion technique and broth dilution technique. Fluconazole and Gentamycin were used as the standard drugs.

The differential pulse polarographic (DPP) measurements were carried out using the ELICO CL362 polarographic analyzer (India). The drop time of 1 s was electronically controlled using a 663 VA stand from the com-

Scheme 2

pany. The polarograms were recorded using a potential rate of 100 mV s^{-1} . A three-electrode system composed of a dropping mercury electrode (DME), saturated calomel electrode (SCE) as reference electrode and platinum wire as an auxiliary electrode were used. The voltammetry experiments were performed using a Autolab type II (Eco-Chemie B.V., Utrecht, The Netherlands) potentiostat-galvanostat with 757 VA computrace software. The utilized electrodes were hanging mercury drop electrode (HMDE) as working electrode, Ag/AgCl as reference electrode and a graphite rod as auxiliary electrode. The electrochemical cell was Metrohm 663 VA stand. Controlled potential electrolysis experiments were performed using an Autolab Potentiostat/Galvanostat PGSTAT Metrohm 663 VA stand as electrochemical cell, fitted with a PC provided the appropriate GPES 4.2 (General Purpose Electrochemical Software). Coulometric experiments were performed in the potentiostatic mode using Pt foil with large surface area as working electrode and a Pt wire, counter electrode. Elemental analysis was carried out on Carlo Erba 1108 analyser. The IR spectra were recorded on Shimadzu, Japan, model prestize IR 20, spectrophotometer, ^1H NMR spectra were recorded on Varian EM-390 MHz NMR spectrometer in $\text{DMSO-}d_6$ using TMS as internal reference and chemical shift values were expressed in ppm d Bruker DRX 300 (300 MHz, FT NMR). The pH of the buffer was checked using a pH meter (Decible DB-1011 digital pH meter) with the help of combined glass calomel electrode.

Procedure for synthesis of compounds :

Synthesis of N-phenylhydrazinecarbothioamide : Thiosemicarbazide has been synthesized in two steps.

Synthesis of phenyl isothiocyanate :

A 500 mL round bottom flask equipped with a mechanical stirrer and a dropping funnel, was cooled in a freezing mixture. A concentrated aqueous ammonia solu-

Table 3. Antimicrobial study of synthesized compounds

Compd.	Diameter of zone of inhibition in mm							
	<i>A. niger</i>		<i>C. albicans</i>		<i>S. aureus</i>		<i>B. antricis</i>	
	200 $\mu\text{g/mL}$	400 $\mu\text{g/mL}$	200 $\mu\text{g/mL}$	400 $\mu\text{g/mL}$	200 $\mu\text{g/mL}$	400 $\mu\text{g/mL}$	200 $\mu\text{g/mL}$	400 $\mu\text{g/mL}$
1	8.3	12.3	9.5	12.5	9.8	13.0	8.3	12.3
2	8.6	12.7	9.4	12.5	9.8	13.3	8.6	12.7
3	8.8	12.9	9.8	12.8	9.8	13.4	8.8	12.9

tion (41 mL) was introduced into the flask through the dropping funnel, followed by carbon disulphide (24 mL) and the resulting mixture was stirred continuously. Aniline (30 mL), dissolved in ethanol (40 mL) was added through the dropping funnel and stirred for about 20 min, till a heavy precipitate of ammonium tolyldithiocarbamate separates out. This salt was transferred into a 5 litre round bottom flask containing 200 mL distilled water. A solution of lead nitrate (90 g in 200 mL water) was added to it and the reaction mixture was continuously stirred till lead sulphide precipitated out. The reaction mixture was subjected to steam distillation. Isothiocyanatobenzene has been separated out from the distillate. Diethyl ether was used to extract white shining crystals of isothiocyanatobenzene.

Synthesis of N-phenylhydrazinecarbothioamide :

Solution of isothiocyanatobenzene (0.1 M) in ethanol was taken in a round bottom flask. A solution of hydrazine hydrate (0.1 M) in ethanol was added to it at once, followed by continuous stirring. An exothermic reaction accompanied by vigorous effervescences was observed. The contents of the flask were refluxed on a water bath for 4–5 h, resulting in the formation of a white precipitate of phenyl thiosemicarbazide, which was filtered and washed repeatedly with ethanol. The product was found to be soluble in dioxane, dimethyl sulphoxide and dimethylformamide. Yield 72%, m.p. 175 °C; IR (KBr) cm^{-1} : 3296 and 3254 (N-H str.), 1277 (C=S str.), 2924 and 2850 (C-H str.).

A solution of phenylhydrazinecarbothioamide (0.001 M; in minimum, quantity of dimethyl formamide) was taken in a flask and 2-hydroxy-benzaldehydes (0.001 M; in dimethyl formamide) was slowly added with continuous stirring. The contents of the flask were refluxed for 8–10 h. The reaction mixture was cooled on an ice-bath and a drop of sulphuric acid was added. On addition of requisite amount of distilled water. The product (2E)-3-(2-hydroxyphenyl)-N-(4-substituted phenyl)triaz-2-ene-1-carbothioamide separated out as a light brown solid. It was repeatedly washed with distilled water and finally with ethanol. The product was found to be soluble in dimethyl sulfoxide and dimethyl form amide. Yield 70%, m.p. 189 °C; IR (KBr) cm^{-1} : 3296 and 3254 (N-H str.), 1277 (C=S str.), 2924 and 2850 (C-H str.). The other

thiosemicarbazone derivatives were synthesized by the aforementioned procedure.

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Jain *et al.* : Electrochemical and biological behaviour of synthesized bioactive *etc.*

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